

Subject: Education**Title: Role of Technology in ADR in post COVID 19 ERA****Author: Dr. Pravita Tripathi**
Assistant professor, Department of political science
RNS Degree college, Sarwa, Kanpur**LYCEUM INDIA****Journal of Social Sciences**

Abstract: Today Era is the age of technology. Education is also the means of this technology systems in crisis of COVID 19 man removed the technology systems whatever is learned or acquired knowledge is called education technology has great importance in human cannot be imagined. Today in the crisis of post COVID 19 through Technology the physical mental intellectual, spiritual power and developed human beings in their lives only by means of technology Achieves the highest goal in the time of COVID pandemic the better Alternative to digital have emerged through technology. Now emerging technology in COVID 19 like education health, energy, environment agriculture, empower the areas of political security, industry etc. for natural innovative s it includes. National and international cyber physical mission system through this many innovation technology centres were developed across the country.

Keywords: COVID 19, WHO, physical education, distance learning, technology education vaccine**Introduction:**

Today in the crisis of post COVID 19 through technology the physical mental, intellectual, spiritual power and developing human being in their lives only by means of technology Achieves the highest goal in the time of COVID pandemic the better Alternative to digital have emerged through technology.

COVID 19 is an intolerable sickness which results in acute respiratory disorders to the infected individual COVID 19 sick ness started from china in November 2019.covid19 characterized as an irresistible malady brought about by another infection. This infection was spread extremely quickly. As report by world health organization (WHO) the complete affirmed instances of COVID 19 overall are 823.626 cases with 40,598 passing (1 April 2020) covid19 advance to every person when they come in contact with infected person during the occurrence of cough and sneezing. Moreover, the COVID 19 virus also infect a person when touches the metallic surface. Which are more prone and a suitable for virus to contaminate. COVID 19 has given noteworthy effected on the monetary advancement around the world with the enormous scope isolates, travel, limitation and social removing measure s drive a sharp fall in shopper and business use. This circumstance was made financial downturn all-inclusive that as it may numerous endeavors have been finished by government so as to lessen the spread of COVID 19 infection. As indicate by WHO (2020) for maintain a strategic distance from contamination and to slow transmission of COVID 19, people are urged to follow the accompanying Recommendations like

- Scrubbing the with soap and applying alcohol mix solution on hand after an hour or so.
- Upholding the distance of 6 foot or 2 meters between every two individuals.
- Avoid contacting your face.
- cover the cavity and nostrils during cough and sneeze and staying home if any person finds himself infected with such symptoms.
- Refrain from the use of cigarettes.
- Avoid the physical indulgence by dodging very far transit movement and
- Cancelling the presence at places where one finds mass collect.

As per world health organization (2020) The most elevated instance of COVID 19 is United State of America that are 163.199 cases and the subsequent nation is Italy with the absolute case are 105,792(2April 2020) subsequent ly.it is significant by follow the recommendation by WHO.

This infection has increased the price of every purchasing item in every nation people liking for basic amenities like food, medical assistant will be as on a high end, on the country, their attention towards apparels or other similar items will drop. This drop will be because of understandable factors for example.

- Deferring of the people, request.
- Conceding the request,
- Lowering of jaunts and.
- shrinkage of monetary and economic shuffling.

1. Distance Learning:

According to survey 2021 Around 191 countries have either implemented or announced the closure school and university. Which has directly impacted close to 1.57 billion students. Most of education institutions have started to offer their courses online to make sure education is not disrupted due to pandemic. Technology used in distant learning include artificial reality,3D printing virtual reality and robot teacher enabled with artificial intelligence

2. Contract tracking application:

Contact Tracking apps like Aarogya setu have assisted in tracking the COVID 19 spread. Technology has also helped in the education people about the entire situation and remaining them to take the necessary precautions. telecom operator such as BSNL, Jio, Airtel, etc. have use caller tunes for spreading awareness about the pandemic the facility recognition technology has helped Identifying people accurately even when They are wearing a mask. Technology has also helped in monitoring the movement of quarantined people.

3. Contactless online delivery:

The online grocery during the pandemic due to the souring demand amongst consumers. Families particularly with children and older people preferred to place their grocery orders online. This is turn resulted in a significant increase of new user we are resorting to online apps for grocery delivery.

4. Online Environment:

COVID 19 has completely transitioned how contact is being generated distributed, and streamed. Online streamed of live shows and concerts have gained traction across the world. Several film production companies have also been releasing. Their movies via over the top OTT platforms such an Amazon, prime video, Hot star, Netflix, Zee5 etc.

5. Robotics technology:

COVID 19 has made us realize how meaningful human interaction are for making things work. The pandemic has severely impacted labor-intensive sector such a food, retail, logistics, and manufacturing business. COVID 19 has resulted in a strong push to implement the usage of robots and also to speed up the Robotics research.

Challenges:

The challenge before us is not less at the level of students', parents Today even though electricity has reached Rural areas, stopping the same cut is also a big challenge. Today only 24 percent of Indians have a smart phone and 11 percent of house hold have some kind of computer device.24 percent of the families have internet in such a situation, due to the new education system, thinking understanding, Sanskrit and the challenges raised in front of the resources are also a big issue. Today the challenges in the way of E learning is as follows E G. Electric City problem internet connection Availability of equipment, gender star etc. Have been found similarly disparity has also been found between status.40 percent of the house hold in Haryana, Punjab, Uttarakhand Have Internet Access Odisha, Andhra Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Jharkhand, Madhya Pradesh And West Bengal. This Ratio has been seen to be less than 20 percent. At the present an Atmosphere of peace is growing all around us Due to the epidemic the density of the relationships between the Guru and the disciple seems to be decreasing in the words of Kabir without self-knowledge, we get all the empty letters of knowledge, through education."

Benefit of technology in the field Education:

At the time of post COVID 19 some new innovations of education were also provided for the students through Technology with were follows-

- 1- National digital Library it has more than 3 crore digital resources available.
- 2- More than 80 Thousand E books were made available for online education at the institution portal.
- 3- CBSE Vidhyadaan, in this free material is available for the students of 6 to 12 video, Audio.
- 4- E-Pathshala has provided 1886 Audio,2000 vedio,996 eBooks 504 Philips books.
- 5- Swayam is an integrated platform, in which 2769 online courses were run for children from 9 to 12 for postgraduate children in which more than1.5 crores children Enrolled.

India has been fully proactive in fighting The COVID 19 pandemic on the other hand the slowdown in trade between India and the Rest of the world acts as a counter-productive due to the epidemic, this Hit of the market is disrupting the supply chain of essential commodities that essential items include COVID 19 test kit, Mask, Alcohol based sanitizer, civilian protection equipment frontline includes dress material for health workers, ventilator s for patients etc.

This was a big challenge due to COVID 19, which was produced in bulk as soon as possible through technology in the event of such a crisis, our government should be Motivated to activate the problem of make in India, as well as various research program of the country. Development R and institutions incorporated to Activate the country's scientific community under the leadership of Dr. Harshvardhan minister of technological science and health science. Adopted a coordinated approach This technology approach has led to sharing of best practices, collaboration of work development of need based innovation and helped to provide a common platform to avoid duplicate of research work to reduce COVID-19, researchers have developed new test kits protective equipment, Breathing, equipment in less time with the help of technology was able to work 24 hours a day role of technological agencies India apex, research agency is DTS and supporting institutions under the Associate ministry from DTS suitable in India to Address the plethora of minds related to COVID 19 technology took the lead in coordinating the effort.

1. Intensification of Research in high priority Areas (IRPHA):

Science And engineering research board Serb, DST is an Autonomous body. Research intensification in upper primary Areas under IRPHA scheme CERB national R and D efforts for epidemiological studies during Autoimmune viral infect competitive proposal for new antiviral with a strong interdisciplinary component were invited for studies on immune response and immunity cured, affordable diagnosis was available against COVID 19 and related viral infection through Technology short term core research Grants special call by SCRB to meet the current needs of health workers.

A- Affordable and proton Rapid diagnostic kit or equipment.

B- computationally identified molecular characterization of COVID 19 verified Drug Reuses against COVID 19 Targets and Nutritional supplements for immunity tasted by prognostic against.

2. Grassroot innovation:

Foundation by individuals and local communities in any technology sector new supports all four at the developed grassroots Level. Along with this to deal with crisis of the epidemic by NSF to the citizens to COVID 19 competition S3 to Adopt creative and innovative ideas through Invited-

- (1) promoting health food and protection for Nutrition.
- (2) Reducing the Transmission of corona virus.
- (3) where ever it is necessary to clean young hands body, house hold items homes public place.
- (4) supply and distribution of essential commodities to women and men living Alone.
- (5) Beneficial Association among people by staying at home.

3. Anti-Microbial coating:

Jawaharlal Nehru for Advanced scientific Research Technology institute under DST A successful cure brought to the Aid of patients. This coating is able to completely kill influenza virus and resistance pathogens Victoria and kabuki is the capable of completely killing All types of Victoria including Methicillin Resistant Staphylococcus, iris, Fluconazole Resistant Albicans, SPP, and a series of viruses have been hypothesized for severe acute respiratory syndrome corona virus-2 (SARS COVID 19) key caring will not Allow micro- organizes to activate on coated surface during the outbreak of COVID 19, the coating is used for personal protection of health workers Applicable can be used to protect clothing.

4. Research proposal passed by TDB:

The technology development Board (TDB) A statutory body under DST has asked Indian companies and enterprises to deal with the COVID 19 pandemic invited proposal to address safety and home-based Respiratory intervention for patients in this critical situation by technology low cost mask, low cost-effective thermal scanning device sanitation in Large Areas as well as contactless entry Rapid, diagnostic kit, non-oxygenator and ventilator facilities were provided.

5. Artificial Manual Breeding Unit (AmBU)

Artificial intelligence at shri Chitra Tirunal institute of medical science and Technology (ScTIMST) Trivandrum development a ventilator system based on Artificial Manual breeding unit (AMBU) with Inputs from the clinical faculty the institute Automated (AMBU) ventilator will help critical patients. Who have ICU ventilator to breath the technology has rapidly gone in to clinical trials and Manufacturing through Wipro Bangalore in addition to this emergency ventilator the institute is trying to develop a Low cost capable digital x-Ray detector for the examination of COVID-19 patients it was done.

Conclusion:

COVID 19 has provided that technology innovations have been helping in managing the epidemic in a timely systematic and clean manner. A lesson Learnt from the COVID 19 pandemic has been to stay prepared well in advance against any crisis at both an individual and collective level. All we need to fight epidemic like COVID 19 is prepared ness. Advancement in technology is steadily progressing.it will undoubtedly centime to grow exponentially.it we human who have to adopt to change in technology faster and Continue to invest in building the technology systems for better prepared ness.

The COVID 19 is brought by the infection serious intense Respiratory disorder coronavirus. The malady is essentially spared between human through respiratory beads from hacks and sniffles. The spreading of COVID 19 add to enormous number of passing40.598 passing by 1April 2020.The spreading of this pandemic makes Alarm among open that add to decrement pattern in the travel industry.

Reference:

- 1- World health organization (2020)
- 2- COVID 19 government public Health mitigation measures (2020)
- 3- center for Disease control and prevention (2020).
- 4- UN News COVID 19 women health and crime year (2020)
- 5- stoker G. (1998) Governance as theory: five propositions, international social science journal Vol.I.No.
- 6- India Today COVID 19 (2020)
- 7- Ghosh.c.c.(2020.may 19) COVID 19 add new dimension to us - china trade war retrieved from [http://www.thehindubusinessline.com/opinion/columns/c-p Chandrasekhar/COVID 19-add.news-demensions-to-us China trade-war/article 31616385.ece](http://www.thehindubusinessline.com/opinion/columns/c-p-Chandrasekhar/COVID-19-add.news-demensions-to-us-China-trade-war/article-31616385.ece).
- 8- BBC 2020 <https://wwwbbc.com/news/world-asia-india-52086274> accessed on 6th April 2020.

Journal of Social Sciences